

Phylogenetic Analysis of *Amanita Pakistanica*, Macrofungus from District Bannu KPK, Pakistan Based on DNA Marker

Zain Ullah Khan

Department of Botany, Islamia College Peshawar, Pakistan

Waqar Ahmad

Agriculture Research Station Bannu, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan

Ihtesham Liaqat

Department of Botany, University of Science & Technology Bannu, Pakistan

Arshad Ullah

Department of Botany, University of Science & Technology Bannu, Pakistan

Umair Niaz

Department of Basic Veterinary Sciences,
University of Veterinary and Animal Sciences, Swat, Pakistan

Abstract

A wild macrofungus, *Amanita pakistanica*, is collected from District Bannu KP, Pakistan. Identification of this taxon is based on the morphological and molecular characterizations. The morphological characteristics such as pileus size, form, color, Basidiomata and scales, stipe length, width and texture, and spore anatomy such as basidiospore, cystidia, basidia, pileipellis and stipitipellus have been studied and found in accordance with characteristics of collection of *A. pakistanica* species. ITS-rDNA that is universal fungal marker of the internal transcribed spacers of ribosomal DNA sequences from local collections have been compared to GenBank database sequences by using BLAST analysis and further the evolutionary affinities of local collection determined by phylogenetic analysis. All the data examined has been found to be in accordance with morpho-anatomical as well as molecular characteristics of *A. pakistanica* collections from Europe and Asia.

Keywords: Toxic mushroom, Amanitaceae, DNA barcoding, Amanita.

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Introduction

Amanita belongs to the class Agaricomycetes and family Amanitaceae, which contains many ectomycorrhizal, saprophytic, and sometimes toxic species widely distributed across the world. The genus is taxonomically complex and diverse, comprising more than 500 described species (Tulloch, 2005; Zhang et al., 2010). Members of *Amanita* are identified by their characteristic morphology, including a universal veil forming a volva at the base of the stipe, a partial veil forming an annulus, free lamellae, and white to pale-colored spore prints. However, despite these distinctive features, many *Amanita* species have

overlapping morphological characteristics that make species-level identification through morphology alone difficult (Corner and Bas, 1962; Yang, 2015).

In Pakistan, the macrofungal diversity is highly remarkable because of varied climatic and ecological zones that range from dry plains to moist temperate forests. In the northwest, particularly Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KP), a number of taxa of macrofungi find a favorable habitat; however, molecular-based characterization and phylogenetic documentation of many species are meagerly available. *Amanita pakistanica* is a rarely reported macrofungus collected from District Bannu, KP, Pakistan, and represents an addition in regional fungal diversity. It is morphologically characterized by a prominent volva, free gills, and white spores, features typical of the genus *Amanita* (Razaq et al., 2012; Ahmad et al., 2014). However, similar morphological features of the *Amanita* species have frequently caused taxonomic confusion that has increased the need for molecular-based approaches for reliable identification and classification.

In recent years, molecular phylogenetic analyses with DNA-based markers have become an effective approach toward resolving taxonomic ambiguities within fungi. The ITS region of nuclear rDNA has been widely accepted as a universal molecular barcode for fungal identification and phylogenetic study (Gardes and Bruns, 1993; Schoch et al., 2012). To date, this marker has been successfully used in estimating evolutionary relationships and species delimitation not only in *Amanita* but also in other Basidiomycetes genera (Cui et al., 2018; Zhang et al., 2010).

Application of molecular tools on fungal taxonomy, although increasing in Pakistan, has been done on only a limited number of *Amanita* species by using DNA markers (Ilyas et al. 2013; Jabeen et al. 2017). Therefore, molecular characterization of *Amanita pakistanica* is necessary to ascertain its taxonomic position and understand its evolutionary relationship with the closely related taxa.

According to phylogenetic analysis, the Pakistani *Amanita* collections can be compared with the reference sequences of related taxa from other parts of the world by the universal ITS marker. The aim of this study is to carry out the phylogenetic analysis of *Amanita pakistanica* collected from District Bannu, KP, Pakistan, based on ITS-nrDNA data. This will provide molecular confirmation of the species, extend the known locality record of *Amanita pakistanica*, and contribute to the understanding of the fungal biodiversity of Pakistan.

Materials and Methods

Morpho-Anatomical Characterization

Fruiting body of mushroom were collected from District Bannu, KPK, Pakistan in the current study. Morphological characters were noted on the spot from collection site, the mushrooms were photographed and a field observation was recorded. The morpho-anatomical collection was characterized following Vellinga 2001. Free hand sections of lamella were prepared for anatomical characters after dipping the material dissolved in 5% KOH solution and observed using light microscope.

Molecular Characterization

For DNA extraction a fragment of dried Basidiomata was extracted and dissolved in CTAB buffer by following protocol of Gardes and Bruns, (1993). Internal Transcribed Spacers (ITS) part of nrDNA was amplified following protocol described by (White et al., 1990; Gardes & Bruns, 1993). For visualizing and sequencing of amplified product, Razaq et al., 2016, 2017 was followed. The sequences were created and edited with the current version of the BioEdit alignment software (Tom Hall, Ibis Biosciences, Carlsbad and California). Local species nucleotide sequence comparisons were carried out using online databases. Molecular Evolutionary Genetics Analysis (CIPRES Science Gateway) software was used to perform sequence alignments and phylogenetic analysis (Tamura et al., 2011). All of the sequences in the study are aligned with the default settings. After completing the BLAST (Basic Local Alignment Search Tool)

closely related sequences were downloaded from GenBank for alignment and phylogenetic analysis. Sequences alignment and phylogenetic tree construction was carried by using MEGA ver. 6.0 software (Tamura et al., 2013). In addition, the alignment was trimmed with conserved motifs to allow for the inclusion of full ITS parts of sequences (Dentinger et al., 2011). On the bases of Jukes-Cantor model of nrITS sequencing, the maximum likelihood (ML) technique used the nearestneighbor-interchange (NNI) heuristic search technique. The bootstrap value of 1000 replicates was used to test the phylogeny. All recently produced sequences were uploaded to GenBank, and in the phylogenetic tree their accession codes also mentioned.

Amanita pakistanica

Morphological Characterization

PILEUS: 7.3 – 6.9 cm in diameter, slightly depressed to plane, moderate yellowish brown (10YR 5/4 #967454), radially with scurfy; curvature uplifted; margin tuberculate striate; LAMELLAE: adnate, thick, crowded, creamy white in color with even margin; STIPE: 11 × 0.8 cm, pale yellow green (5GY 9/12 #E7E6CF), centrally attached, flared to bulbous, cartilage like, smooth, nature of pith is solid; ANNULUS: superior, creamy white, rudimentary to upturned; VOLVA: circumscissile. (Figure 1)

Anatomical Characterization

BASIDIOSPORES: (8) 10 – 12 (13) × 7 (8) – 9(10) μm [X = 10.2 × 8.6 μm, Q = 1.18], sub globose, smooth, thin-walled, apiculate, light green gutiulate, reddish in congo red color; BASIDIA: 29 – 45 × 10 – 14 μm, clavate, thick walled, with sterigmata, red in congo red color; CHEILOCYSTIDIA: 23 – 32 × 8 – 11 μm, clavate, thick walled, red, guttulate; PLEUROCYSTIDIA: 26 – 42 × 7 – 14 μm, clavate, red in congo red, thick-walled; PILEIPELLIS: 7 – 10 μm in diameter, intericate trichoderm, thin-walled, pinkish in congo red; STIPETIPELLUS: 6 – 17 μm thin-walled, red in congo red, intericate trichoderm to trichoderm. (Figure 1)

Material Examined

Pakistan, Khyber PakhtunKhwa, District, Bannu, 18-08-2024.

Figure 1. Morphological and Anatomical Feature of *Amanita pakistanica*;

A-B: 3.8 cm; C: 10 μm; D: 10 μm; E: 35 μm; F: 10 μm; H: 35 μm.

**A-B: Basidiomata; C: Basidiospore; D: Basidia; E: Stipetipellus; F: Cheilocystidia;
G: Pleurocystidia; H: Pileipellis**

Molecular Phylogenetic Analysis

The internal transcribed space (ITS) of this particular species comprises of 619 base pairs. Upon performing a preliminary search of the GENBANK database, it was found that *Amanita pakistanica* (MW425334) is the closest relative to this species. The search results showed a 100% Query Coverage, an expect value of 0.0, and a percent identity index of 100%.

The MUSCLE Alignment tool aligned the newly generated *Amanita pakistanica* internal transcribed spacer (ITS) with 34 nucleotide sequences obtained from GENBANK by BLAST search. The Phylogenetic Tree was constructed using the RAxML (Randomized Axelerated Maximum Likelihood) algorithm, accessed through the CIPRES Science Gateway online portal, the topology with a log likelihood of 1000 was selected. The number of substitutions per unit used to scale the tree. Of these characters, 471 were conserved, 264 were variable, 185 were informative for parsimony, and 77 singletons. The current analysis involved the treatment of 34 nucleotide sequences. All positions that had gaps and missing data were removed. The final dataset consisted of a total of 899 positions. The tree is distinguished by the presence of two distinct clades, namely Clade A and Clade B. Clade A consists of *Amanita tlaxcalipanther*, *Amanita pantherine*, *Amanita subglobosa*, *Amanita pakistanica*, and *Amanita albocreata* with a bootstrap value of 100. In comparison, Clade B comprises taxa with a bootstrap value of 63. The composition of the group includes *Amanita citrinoindusiat*, *Amanita spissa*, and *Amanita rubescens*. The species *Zhuliangomyces olivaceus* is employed as an outgroup (Figure 2 and Table 1).

Figure 2. Phylogenetic Tree of *Amanita pakistanica* Based on ITS-DNA Marker Using Maximum Likelihood Method. The Numerical Numbers Mentioned on Branch Node Represent Bootstrap Values. Studied Sequences in Current Research have been Labeled with a Vox

Table 1. Taxa of *Amanita pakistanica* Included in the Molecular Phylogenetic Analyses

S. no.	Species Name	Specimen voucher / isolate	Locality	Gene Bank No.	Submitted by
1	<i>Amanita albocreata</i>	RET 547-7	Canada	KU248128	Tulloss,R.E.
2	<i>Amanita albocreata</i>	RET 263-4	USA	KU248130	Tulloss,R.E.
3	<i>Amanita albocreata</i>	iNat87961925	USA	ON713806	Plischke,J.
4	<i>Amanita albocreata</i>	RET 054-8	USA	KU248127	Tulloss,R.E.
5	<i>Amanita albocreata</i>	RET 031-5	USA	KU248124	Tulloss,R.E.
6	<i>Amanita citrinoindusiat</i>	HKAS100522	China	MH508320	Cui,Y.Y.
7	<i>Amanita citrinoindusiat</i>	HKAS58796	China	MH508321	Cui,Y.Y.
8	<i>Amanita citrinoindusiat</i>	HKAS58884	China	MH508323	Cui,Y.Y.
9	<i>Amanita citrinoindusiat</i>	HKAS58874	China	MH508322	Cui,Y.Y.
10	<i>Amanita citrinoindusiat</i>	HKAS58886	China	MH508324	Cui,Y.Y.
11	<i>Amanita pakistanica</i>	MAK:UTK:34	Pakistan	OR625722	Khan,Z.
12	<i>Amanita pakistanica</i>	SUA270	Pakistan	MW425333	Ullah,S.
13	<i>Amanita pakistanica</i>	RET 352-1	Pakistan	KX061525	Tulloss,R.E.
14	<i>Amanita pakistanica</i>	SUA225	Pakistan	MW425332	Ullah,S.
15	<i>Amanita pakistanica</i>	SUA273	Pakistan	MW425334	Ullah,S.
16	<i>Amanita pakistanica</i>	RET 411-7	India	MG991745	Tulloss,R.E.
17	<i>Amanita pakistanica</i>	RET 317-6	Pakistan	KX365198	Tulloss,R.E.
18	<i>Amanita pantherine</i>	NAMA 1998-002	USA	MK580760	Russell,S.D.
19	<i>Amanita pantherine</i>	DAVFP:29323	NA	JF899547	Guichon,S.H.A.
20	<i>Amanita pantherine</i>	OSC 1064065	USA	EU525997	Smith,J.E.
21	<i>Amanita pantherine</i>	LG307	USA	EU909452	Pringle,A.
22	<i>Amanita pantherine</i>	45929(NY)	NA	AB080784	Oda,T.
23	<i>Amanita rubescens</i>	NDES_F416 NVE160	Colombia	FJ890031	Vargas,N.
24	<i>Amanita rubescens</i>	JMP0003	NA	EU819464	Palmer,J.M.
25	<i>Amanita rubescens</i>	TRTC156957	Canada	JN020972	Dentinger,B.T.
26	<i>Amanita spissa</i>	KA12-0884	South Korea	KF245910	Kim,C.S.
27	<i>Amanita spissa</i>	UP542	NA	EF493271	Nyrgren,C.M.
28	<i>Amanita spissa</i>	UP541	NA	EF493270	Nyrgren,C.M.
29	<i>Amanita subglobosa</i>	MHHNU 31084	NA	MK239245	Zhang,P.
30	<i>Amanita subglobosa</i>	JL4	NA	ON059314	Gao,J.
31	<i>Amanita subglobosa</i>	RET 717-5	India	KX810031	Tulloss,R.E.
32	<i>Amanita subglobosa</i>	HKAS122564	China	ON794372	Wang,R.
33	<i>Amanita tlaxcalipanther</i>	Mushroom Observer 428566	USA	MZ354631	Clements,T.A.
34	<i>Amanita tlaxcalipanther</i>	Mushroom Observer 428571	USA	MW633035	Clements,T.A.
35	<i>Zhuliangomyces olivaceus</i>	HKAS101960	China	MH561739	Cui,Y.-Y.

Discussion

The Amanitaceae family is diverse and encompasses a broad array of fungi. Several distinctive species have been discovered in this family, which include but are not limited to *Amanita aurantialba*, *Amanita indovaginata*, and *Amanita pseudohemibapha* originating from India (Ghosh et al., 2023). In addition, in India, a new species of Amanita, *Amanita sharmae*, belonging to the *Amanita sect. vaginatae*, was discovered (Kantharaja & Krishnappa, 2022). *Amanita coryli* is another species of the same family that has been traced in the Balkan Peninsula and Turkey; this shows that its range could be more considerable than what is considered (Kumar et al., 2023). Three species of Amanita mushrooms are reported in Thailand, specifically *A. aureofloccosa*, *A. manicata*, and a newly discovered species named *A. albicarnosa* (Bozok et al., 2023). Many mycologists have tried to divide this large agaricoid family, Amanitaceae, into sections, subgenera, and genera (Corner & Bas, 1962). The Amanitaceae family has five generally acknowledged

genera: *Amanita*, *Catarrama*, *Limacella*, *Myxoderma*, and *Limacellopsis*. Of these, the genus *Amanita* is most famous and easily recognizable (Cui et al., 2018).

Amanita pakistanica belongs to the family Amanitaceae. Its small to medium-sized basidiomata have white or pale-yellow edges with an off-white to dull yellow pileus in the middle. The base of the unmarked stipe is covered with a universal veil made up of white granular warts. The basidiospores of *Amanita pakistanica* are ellipsoid or broadly ellipsoid. The first record of this species came from Pakistan. Some other species, such as *Amanita pseudosychonopyramis* and *Amanita parvipantherina*, belong to the genus *Amanita* and show similarities with *Amanita pakistanica*. However, it can be differentiated based on various morphological features such as cap colour, universal veil remnants, basidiospore size, and shape (Kumar et al., 2023). Several fundamental differences come forth when the *Amanita pakistanica* that I collected from Utror Valley is compared to the species collected by Kumar et al. (2021) in India. First of all, my collection shows a greater pileus diameter while attaining a moderate yellowish brown colour which is quite prominent as compared to their collection, showing a smaller and lighter-coloured pileus. Besides this, there is a big difference between the characteristics of the stipe. The length of the stipe of the species I collected is longer, with a pale yellow-green colour, while their species has a white coloured stipe. The presence of a circumscissile volva in our collection species is just opposite to the presence of remains of a universal veil in their species. Moreover, in our collection sub globose basidiospores were present while their specimen showed basidiospores that were broadly ellipsoid to ellipsoid in shape. Microscopically, both the species can further be differentiated based on the differences in the size and features of the basidia, cystidia, and pileipellis. These differences highlight the distinct morphological features of our collection species from their species.

A comparison with Tulloss et al. (2001) reveals various physical differences between my collection and theirs. Their collection had a larger pileus, coloration, and lacked a circumscissile volva, unlike mine. My stipe size, colour, and superior annulus are unique. The presence of the universal veil separates the two species, whereas the other one has a volva that is circumscissile while mine lack any veil. The nature of the lamellae attachment, thickness, and colour segregates the two species. Lastly, the basidiospore size, cystidia, and pileipellis/stipitipellus morphology separates my species from their species. These morphological differences confirm each species' taxonomic distinctiveness. The ITS in this particular species consists of 619 nucleotide base pairs. An initial search against the GENBANK database indicated that *Amanita pakistanica* (MW425334) is a sister species to this subject of study. The search results yielded a Query Coverage of 100%, an expect value of 0.0, and a percent identity index of 100%.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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